

Studies on the Synthesis and Properties of Boron Stabilised Carbanions[#]

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In recent years, one of the most significant developments which has profoundly added new dimensions to the organoboron chemistry has been the production of carbanions α -to boron. One attractive approach for production of carbanions involves the use of highly hindered organoboranes such as dimesitylmethylborane. On this basis a large number of bifunctional boron complexes of the type $\text{Me}_2\text{BCH}_2\text{MeR}_x$ have been synthesised. Salient features of their synthesis and applications are presented.

The term 'Carbanion' generally refers to a species in which part of the unit negative charge resides on a certain carbon atom. The negative charge can vary and may be decreased, i.e. the carbanion may be stabilised by :

- (i) Covalent bonding to the accompanying metal cation : $\text{M}^{\delta+}-\text{C}^{\delta-}$ (e.g. in Grignard reagents $\text{R}^{\delta-}-\text{Mg}^{\delta+}$; organocopper, organozinc, organolithium reagents).
- (ii) π -Conjugation allowing the charge to reside largely on an atom more electronegative than carbon, such as oxygen atom of a ketone, i.e. enolate anion,

- (iii) π -Conjugation to other carbon atoms, as in acetylides. Thus, in 1-alkynes, due to higher electronegativity of carbon in sp hybridization state, terminal hydrogen can be easily removed,

- (iv) Inductive effects from adjacent heteroatoms, e.g. S, O, N, Si, Se, B or X.
- (v) d -Orbital overlap as in some ylids. This usually involves N, P, S, Se or As, stabilising a carbon by bearing a formal positive charge,

Carbanions stabilised by α -heteroatom are many and various types, and are powerful synthetic tools in organic synthesis¹. Their use can be represented by two general equations,

where, M = heteroatom and E^+ = electrophilic. The heteroatoms may be attached to an sp^3 carbon (eq. 1) or to an

sp^2 carbon (eq. 2). Heteroatoms generally used include N, O, Si, P, S, Se, Cl, Br and B which has emerged very rapidly in the last ten years. Less common examples include As, Sn, Tl, Ge, Pb and Sb.

The carbanions may be synthesised in two general ways. In a redox process : A metal may donate electrons to a reducible substrate which may then lose a hydride or halide ion leaving a carbanion (with cation partner),

In an acid-base reaction : A proton may be abstracted from a carbon by a negatively charged base leaving a negative charge on that carbon,

Various bases can be used : hydroxide bases (NaOH, KOH), alkoxide base (NaOEt), lithium bases $n\text{-BuLi}$, s - and $t\text{-BuLi}$, $\text{N}(\text{Li})=\text{LiTMP}$, and miscellaneous bases KH, NaH.

Boron stabilised carbanions

Pross *et al.*² carried out calculations on a series of anions XCH_2^- (Table 1).

TABLE 1-CALCULATED STABILISATION ENERGIES (kcal mol^{-1}) FOR CARBANIONS XCH_2^-

X	Stabilisation energy	X	Stabilisation energy
Li	13.7-25.8	F	14.6-16.1
BeH	38.1-46.9	CN	55.0-57.9
BH_2	61.4-71.8	NO_2	75.9-98.1
CH_3	1.4-3.3	CF_3	37.0-57.0
NH_2	3.3-5.6	CHO	60.5-71.5
OH	7.9-10.9	C_6H_5	37.6-44.4

[#]Dr. Ghanshyam Srivastava Memorial Lecture (1995) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on 27 December 1996 at Coimbatore.

Not surprisingly a strong stabilising effect is calculated for π -accepting systems, which for inorganic groups, reaches a peak of 61.4–71.8 kcal mol⁻¹ for planar BH₂.CH₂ :

Delocalisation of the carbanion lone-pair into the empty orbital of the boron means that the boron atom achieves coordinative saturation. This stabilisation effect by BH₂ group is exactly of the same order 60.5–71.5 kcal mol⁻¹ as the stabilization calculated for the CHO group. This raises an important question. Why is that carbanions α -to a carbonyl group commonly known as enolate anion are of paramount importance in organic chemistry (e.g. the Aldol condensation) whereas carbanions α -to a boron atom have been made only recently and hence, as yet, found little application ?

The answer lies in the problem of the formation of carbanions adjacent to boron rather than their stabilisation or reactivity. The usual method for production of carbanions α -to a carbonyl group is proton abstraction by suitable base, e.g. in the aldol condensation, a base like hydroxide ion (OH⁻) or aluminium t-butoxide attacks the α -carbon to produce the corresponding enolate ion which then attacks the carbonyl carbon of another molecule to give the product—a β -hydroxy aldehyde (an aldol) or ketone.

With organoboranes, however, this process must compete with essentially irreversible attack by the base on the boron atom itself to form a coordinatively saturated *ate*-complex; which is generally the preferred pathway³,

Thus the problem of producing carbanions α -to boron by proton abstraction reduces to the problem of preferentially discouraging the *ate*-complex formation. Only a few approaches to the production of carbanions α -to boron have been tried so far and these are outline below.

Use of a highly hindered base :

The first method tried was by Rathke and Kow⁴ using a highly hindered base such as lithium 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-piperilide (LiTMP). They prepared the first boron-stabilised carbanion in 75% from moderately hindered borane, B-methyl-9-BBN (borobicyclononane) at low temp. (-78°). The anion was subsequently quenched with cyclohexanone in what is now known as the boron analogue of the Wittig reaction,

Cleavage of *gem*-dibora compounds :

The most useful reaction of this type was introduced by George Zweifel *et al.*⁵,

Use of boronic esters :

This method has been developed by Matteson and Moody⁶, and it is based on the principle that if certain heteroatoms which are capable of π -back donation (such as oxygens) are attached to boron, then it would discourage *ate*-complex formation. However, stabilisation of an adjacent carbanion would also decrease and there would be competition between the two effects. After long experimentation, it has been finally shown by Matteson that stabilisation can be achieved by the use of two dialkoxyborane units per methylene (CH₂) group. Applying this principle, Matteson *et al.* have developed some useful synthetic methods :

Use of hindered organoboranes :

This approach has been developed and used by Pelter⁷ over the last decade and it involves the use of triorganylboranes. It has been shown by Brown and Dodson⁸ that triphenylborane can be readily oxidised, hydrolysed, and forms complexes with most bases, whereas trimesitylborane undergoes none of these reactions, tri(α -naphthylborane) is intermediate in reactivity,

Reagent	TPB	TNB	TMB
NH ₃	Forms 1:1 addition compd.	Forms 1:1 addition compd.	No Rx
Et ₃ N	Forms 1:1 addition compd.	Forms 1:1 addition compd.	No Rx
Sod. methoxide	Forms NaOMe salt	Forms NaOMe salt	No Rx
Water (Cold, Hot)	Reacts rapidly	No reaction in cold	No Rx

This result was ascribed to steric shielding of the boron by a cage of six *ortho*-methyl groups⁹. Furthermore, it has been shown by Glogowski *et al.*¹⁰ on the reaction of aryl-dimesitylboranes with methoxide, that with four *ortho*-methyl groups, *ate*-complex formation takes place. However, when five or six *ortho*-methyl groups are present no *ate*-complex formation occurs. Thus, steric shielding can prevent *ate*-complex formation.

However, this shielding of boron should not be such efficient as in trimesitylborane. From synthetic point of view, it is not enough to produce and manipulate a carbanion. At some stage the boron must be removed to leave a modified organic moiety and this frequently involves prior *ate*-complex formation. Hence those compounds would be useful in which boron has been sufficiently shielded to in-

hibit *ate*-complex formation with moderately hindered bases but would form complexes with bases of small steric requirements. For this purpose alkyl-dimesitylboranes have been chosen which are readily produced as shown below :

As mentioned earlier, at some stage the boron must be removed to produce simple organic moieties and some of the best methods reported in the literature¹¹ are given below. In summary, under certain conditions, the organyl group of triorganylboranes can be transferred to other atoms such as C, N, O, X :

Of these transformations, the alkaline H₂O₂ oxidation of organoboranes is perhaps the best known method for the removal of boron from organic materials and the yield of the alcohol is almost quantitative.

Reaction of Mes₂BCH₃ with *n*-BuLi gives only *ate*-complex with no trace of anion. Both *s*-BuLi and *t*-BuLi react by a transfer of a β -hydrogen atoms to give lithium dimesitylmethyl hydroborate. The same class of compounds were produced by reaction with sodium hydride or potassium in THF.

However, mesityllithium (readily prepared from bromomesitylene and *t*-butyl lithium) acts as an excellent base with no β -hydrogen atoms and quantitatively yields

Like this, Rathke and Kow⁴ reported the first Boron-Wittig reaction,

Thus reaction of anions $\text{Mes}_2\text{BCH}_2^-$ with various aldehydes and ketones have been investigated^{14,15}. Representative examples are shown below :

Hetero-atoms substituted dimesitylborylmethanes :

The effects of a second hetero-atom on the α -carbon would be of significance since such novel compounds could be useful for various synthetic purposes. Hence a series of new bifunctional organometallic compounds (1-8; Table 3) have been prepared¹⁶ that could give rise to interesting and synthetically valuable processes :

Met = Si, Sn, Pb, S, Se

TABLE 3

Compd. no.	Eq. of preparation	R _x MCl	Product	Yield %	M.p. °C
1	3	Me ₃ SiCl	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SiMe ₃	90	72-73
2	3	Me ₃ SnCl	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SnMe ₃	83	41-43
3	3	ⁿ Bu ₃ SnCl	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SnBu ₃	75	Oil
4	3	Ph ₃ SnCl	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SnPh ₃	76	124
5	3	Ph ₃ PbCl	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ PbPh ₃	60	122
6	3, 4	PhSO ₂ -SPh	Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SPh	60	113
7	3		Mes ₂ BCH ₂ SePh	40	Oil
8	5	HgCl ₂	(Mes ₂ BCH ₂) ₂ Hg	48	180

For compounds 1-5, the component R_xMetX was the corresponding triorganylmetal chloride. However, attempts to make 6 by use of PhSCl failed completely as did use of (PhS)₂. The former reagent gave a number of products whilst the latter seemed reluctant to react. Use of PhSSO₂-Ph, however, did eventually led to a reproducible synthesis of 6 via equation (1).

Because of the problems we encountered in the synthesis of 6 using equation (3), we turned to equation (4) particularly because PhSCH₂Li is a readily available carbanion¹⁷. Reaction was slow but reproducible to give an isolated yield of 60% of pure (6),

Compound 7 was obtained by reaction with *N*-phenylselenium phthalimide via equation (3).

Reactions of bifunctional heteroatom compounds (1-8) :

Reaction with protic reagents : When stoichiometric amounts of neat 1-8 were mixed with equimolar amounts of protic reagents H₂O, MeOH, EtOH, PhOH, BuⁿNH₂, PhSH, PrⁿSH as 0.01 M solutions in THF for 24 h at room temperature, they were recovered unchanged with one exception, the reactions of the thiols with compound 8 were quantitative and complete in 2 h,

The lack of reactivity of compounds 1-8 to air and protic reagents emphasises that they are convenient and readily handled laboratory reagents.

Anion formation : Anion formation was next examined. Compound 1 reacts with either MesLi or LiNChX₂ to give 12 [$\delta_{\text{B}}(\text{THF}) = 41.7$] in quantitative yield as shown by further methylation and deuteration as well as by ¹¹B NMR comparison¹⁸. Similarly, 6 reacts with MesLi to give quantitative yield of the corresponding anion 13 [$\delta_{\text{B}}(\text{THF}) = 39.2$] :

6

13

Both 12 and 13 were taken into diglyme and investigated by variable temperature ¹³C NMR. If most of the stabilisation of these anions is due to the adjacent boron atom they can be described as shown in structure 14 and the *ortho*-methyl groups should be differentiated :

In practice, at room temperature, the *ortho*-methyl groups of both 12 and 13 give two sharp singlets of equal intensity around δ 21.2 and 22.6 ppm which do not coalesce even upto 140°, above which observation was not possible due to thermal degradation. This gives a rotational barrier of >98 kJ mol⁻¹ for these anions, similar to isoelectronic compounds Mes₂BNHR¹⁹. Thus we conclude that the major part of the stabilisation of 12 and 13 is due to the α -boron atom.

In case of tin compounds, 2 and 3 undergo C-Sn cleavage and produce 15 and 16 in the ratio 1 : 1 and we did not succeed in finding conditions that led exclusively to (16) :

However, it was possible to form the desired anion 17 from compound 4 and benzylate to yield 18 :

It was of interest to see whether C-Sn cleavage of 4 could be effected. Compound 4 was therefore treated with one equivalent of PhSLi in THF for 24 h at room temperature, on the expectation of attack on the thiophilic tin atom. In fact only 20% of 19 was produced showing that 4 is particularly resistant to C-Sn cleavage :

Alkylation of the anion Mes₂BCHSPH : A most unusual reaction of electrophilic attack on sulphur in α -thiocarbanions :

Using either mesityllithium or lithium dicyclohexylamide it was possible to quantitatively convert Mes₂BCH₂SPh (6) into its anion (13) which was then reacted with heptyl iodide in THF in a reaction designed to give 20. However, alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidation of the product gave no octaldehyde (21) and only a trace of the hydrolysed product (22) was obtained. Instead a 96% yield of heptyl phenyl sulphide (23) was obtained. A similar result was obtained using simple alkaline hydrolysis which became the standard procedure. The results of reaction of the anion (13) with benzyl iodide were similar to give benzyl phenyl sulphide and phenethyl phenyl sulphide in 5 : 2 ratio.

From these results it appears that carbanion 13 must be alkylated at sulphur to give sulphur ylid 24 rather than 20 which upon alkaline hydrolysis produces heptyl phenyl sulphide (23). Direct heptylation of (6) proceeded by slow attack on sulphur to give 27% yield of 25, this being quite slower than attack on carbanion (13).

In view of these results we studied the well-known thioanisole anion¹⁷ (26) to see whether this simple carbanion would undergo attack on sulphur as well as on carbon :

The ratio of 22 v/s 23 was taken as minimum guide of attack on carbon v/s attack on sulphur (Table 4).

TABLE 4—HEPTYLATION OF LITHIUM PHENYLTHIOMETHANE (9)

Base	Solvent	23 : 22	Base	Solvent	23 : 22
n-BuLi	THF	<0.1 : 97	PhLi	THF	1 : 72
	Glyme	1 : 96		Glyme	1 : 3
	Ether	1 : 12		Ether	2 : 1

Clearly the ratio of products is solvent-dependent. So far we have no clearcut answer to these problems and calculations on charge distribution are under study. In any case, to our knowledge, this reaction has no precedent in the literature, and we believe that this is the first time that there has been a definition of electrophilic attack on a heteroatom (sulphur) α -to a carbanion rather than on the carbon of the carbanion.

The above results clearly demonstrate the utility of the boron stabilised carbanions and further work in this direction is currently under progress in our laboratories.

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